

Improving energy efficiency in IOT Network through green cloud computing and machine learning

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1. Background and motivations

Over the last decade, the number of Internet-enabled gadgets has increased dramatically. The Internet of Things (IoT) technology is critical for enabling enormous machine communications and supporting a wide range of smart applications. These applications include smart buildings, smart cities, smart cars, environmental sensing and forecasting, and catastrophe management. IoT enables real-time data gathering, analysis, and response by permitting seamless connectivity between devices, hence increasing efficiency and effectiveness across different domains. IoT optimizes energy use and increases security in smart buildings, while it improves traffic management and public services in smart cities. Smart automobiles benefit from IoT by incorporating increased safety measures

life by increasing convenience, safety, and resource management. The rapid growth of IoT devices has led in a significant rise in the number of devices per square kilometer in big IoT networks, which can exceed one million devices. As a result, the amount of data created by these devices has increased dramatically and is anticipated to rise further in the future. This increase in data volume and network congestion is a huge challenge to IoT devices, which frequently have limited computational capability. This constraint makes it difficult to evaluate, process, and store the massive amounts of data produced by IoT devices [2]. Furthermore, most of the IoT-based devices rely on battery power, which can quickly run out due to the high energy demands of computationally intensive applications that

and autonomous driving capabilities. Environmental sensing and forecasting rely on IoT for precise data to monitor and predict changes, whereas disaster management systems employ IoT to detect and respond to situations quickly, thereby safeguarding lives and

The seamless integration of IoT improves daily solutions may include advances in energy-efficient hardware, optimized communication protocols, and novel data processing methods. By focusing on these areas, researchers seek to extend battery life, reduce energy consumption, and improve overall performance of IoT devices, allowing them to handle growing data loads and communication needs more efficiently[3].

1.1 Computing Technology

The computing technology is regarded as an excellent technique to conserve power supply for IoT devices. It enables high-performance computation and large-capacity storage to support data collecting and processing in IoT networks. Furthermore, fog and edge computing devices can minimize the stress on cloud servers by executing computations closer to the end device, resulting in lower computation latency[4].

As a result, computing plays an important role in the functioning of vast IoT networks, performing key computation jobs. Considering the significant energy consumption of computing devices and

require low latency and real-time responses. The challenge of conserving or maximizing device energy for IoT devices is therefore an important one that researchers plan to address in the near future. To ensure the long-term viability and effectiveness of IoT networks,

are utilized efficiently while maintaining dependability and scalability. Energy-efficient computing attempts to reduce power consumption and increase the operating life of IoT devices, making IoT networks more sustainable and effective in dealing with large-scale data and compute needs[5].

1.3 Comparison and our contributions

Energy efficiency in IoT networks has been extensively studied, with many studies concentrating on algorithms and strategies at various network levels and components. Several survey articles have been published on energy efficiency issues, such as green IoT networks, cloud computing, fog computing, edge computing, and energy harvesting methods. However, to the best of our knowledge, none of these studies have completely covered all types of green computing (edge, fog, and cloud) and their significance in enabling energy-efficient IoT networks. Massive IoT networks provide considerable difficulties to energy efficiency. Green edge computing (EC), green fog

applications, task offloading is commonly employed to conserve energy. This necessity draws attention to energy-efficient computers, sometimes known as green computing. The basic goal of energy-efficient computing is to ensure that computing resources

recommendations and suggests possible future routes for researchers working on energy-efficient computing[6].

1.2 Overview of computing technologies

Computing technologies have evolved as a critical component of the IoT network landscape, enabling long-term huge IoT networks. Due to the IoT devices have limited computational capacity and energy resources, and the increased data traffic and network congestion have made data processing and analysis difficult for these devices. To solve this difficulty, energy-efficient computing technologies such as edge computing (EC), fog computing (FC), and cloud computing (CC) have been developed to allow for efficient data processing and analysis in IoT networks[7].

1.3.1 Edge Computing (EC)

Edge computing (EC) is a distributed computing paradigm that allows processing and data storage to occur closer to the data source, lowering latency and network congestion. EC devices are positioned at the network's edge and are responsible for real-time data processing and analysis.

computing (FC), and green cloud computing (CC) are the primary focus areas of this study, which provides a summary of recent research on attaining energy efficiency through computing technologies for vast IoT networks. Furthermore, this study makes

increasing overall network efficiency.

However, EC has limitations, which include limitations on the processing power and storage capacity of edge devices. These limits limit the types of tasks that can be carried out at the edge. Despite these restrictions, EC is an important part of the IoT ecosystem, particularly for applications that require fast data processing and low latency replies.

Applications of Edge Computing (EC)

Edge computing (EC) enables autonomous vehicles to evaluate sensor data in real-time, leading to faster decision-making and safer navigation.

Industrial Processes: EC allows for better real-time monitoring and management of industrial equipment, minimizing downtime and enhancing operational efficiency.

Smart Cities: EC can analyze data from numerous sensors in metropolitan areas to improve traffic management, energy efficiency, and public safety systems.

Limitations of Edge Computing

Limited Processing Power: Edge devices

This technique is especially beneficial in applications requiring minimal latency, such as driverless vehicles and real-time monitoring of industrial processes. Furthermore, EC minimizes the quantity of data that must be transferred to the cloud, alleviating network congestion and

amounts of data[8].

Scalability Issues: Managing and scaling a large number of edge devices can be difficult, necessitating strong infrastructure and management procedures.

Fog computing (FC)

Fog computing (FC) is a distributed computing paradigm that, like edge computing (EC), allows processing and data storage to occur closer to the data source. The primary distinction between FC and EC is their place within the network architecture and their different capabilities.

Applications and Advantages Smart Cities:

FC can handle and process data from multiple sensors and IoT devices throughout a city, optimizing traffic flow, energy consumption, and public safety systems.

Healthcare: In healthcare applications, FC can analyze patient data in real time, allowing for faster diagnostic and treatment decisions.

Telecommunications: FC is used in telecom networks to improve network performance, manage traffic, and ensure service quality.

often have lower computing capability than centralized cloud servers, limiting the complexity of tasks they can perform.

Storage Constraints: Edge devices' storage capacity is likewise limited, which can be problematic for applications that create huge

computing paradigm that allows computation and data storage to take place in the cloud, making them accessible to IoT devices from anywhere in the world. CC provides almost limitless processing power and storage capacity, and it is in charge of executing data processing and analysis activities that are beyond the capability of edge and fog computing (FC) devices.

Key Characteristics of Cloud Computing

1. **Centralization:** Cloud computing's key characteristics include centralization. Unlike edge and fog computing, CC concentrates resources in massive data centers. This centralization enables the consolidation of significant computing and storage resources.
2. **Scalability:** CC is highly scalable, allowing users to add or decrease resources as needed without requiring major upfront infrastructure investments.
3. **Accessibility:** IoT devices and applications may access cloud

Limitations of Fog computing (FC)

Implementing and administering a fog computing infrastructure can be costly and difficult, necessitating advanced networking and management technologies[9].

Cloud computing (CC)

The cloud computing (CC) is a centralized

Enterprise Solutions:

Many firms rely on CC for enterprise resource planning (ERP), customer relationship management (CRM), and other large-scale commercial applications.

Benefits of Cloud Computing

➤ **Resource Abundance:**

The CC offers virtually unlimited computational and storage resources, making it suitable for applications with high processing demands.

➤ **Cost Efficiency:**

By using a pay-as-you-go model, CC allows organizations to optimize costs, only paying for the resources they actually use.

➤ **Maintenance and Management:**

The CC providers handle infrastructure maintenance, updates, and security, reducing the operational burden on users.

Therefore, the computing infrastructure resources in the IoT network are organized hierarchically, with cloud computing/servers having the most resources available, followed by FC/nodes, which have a moderate amount of resources and serve as an intermediary layer

resources from anywhere, allowing for global connectivity and data access.

Applications and Advantages

Big Data Analytics:

CC is perfect for applications that demand the processing and analysis of large datasets,

require low latency and real-time processingsuch as those used in social media, e-commerce, and science research.

Machine Learning and AI:

CC's considerable processing capability enables the development and implementation of complicated machine learning models and AI algorithms. limited processing power and storage space. FC is appropriate for applications requiring low latency and real-time processing, but with greater processing power and storage capacity than edge computing.

Hence, CC is an appropriate for applications requiring enormous volumes of while havingdata processing and analysis which can further improve the energy efficiency in computing.

Empowering energy savings techniques for computing environments

This section discusses various ways for optimizing energy utilization in EC, FC, and CC situations without compromising

between CC and edge computing/devices, which have the fewest resources[9]

The type of computer technology used in IoT networks is determined by the unique application needs. EC is appropriate for applications that

networks, two approaches are usually employed:

(i) energy harvesting and (ii) energy saving.

(i) **Energy harvesting**

The energy harvesting can be described as the mechanisms employed to produce energy from a network ambient environment to provide an uninterrupted power supply for the network devices.

(ii) The energy saving schemes On the other hand, energy saving schemes focus on developing algorithms, protocols and even hardware solutions to minimize the network energy consumption and maximize its lifetime. Based on these two categories, on developing algorithms, protocols and even hardware solutions to minimize the network energy consumption and maximize its lifetime.

We categorized energy-saving solutions according to the technologies they use. Compared to previous energy management surveys, our survey includes new intelligent energy-saving approaches that use Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) to cut energy usage in IoT networks.

performances such as energy-aware architecture and data aggregation. The various optimizations include compression, low-power hardware, scheduling, task offloading, unused resource switching, virtualization, energy harvesting, and cooling.

In order to tackle the energy issues in IoT

4.1 Energy Harvesting Techniques

In case of energy harvesting techniques ,the various energy harvesting approaches have to be discussed that have been proposed in the literature, with a focus on the most current options.

4.1.1 Mobile Energy Transfer The mobile energy transfer (MET) is a relatively new approach for capturing energy from IoT networks.

It involves using mobile entities, such as robots or drones, to wirelessly deliver energy to IoT devices. This strategy seeks to address the constraints of existing energy sources by offering a flexible and dynamic alternative for powering IoT networks.

The strategy to minimize a mobile base station's total energy consumption while meeting the data and energy demands of IoT devices to provide Quality of Service (QoS).

This study demonstrates that a variety of parameters can influence the energy consumption of MET-based IoT networks, including the location and movement speed of

We highlight energy-efficient data gathering strategies utilized in IoT networks, as well as sleep/wake-up schemes such as Duty Cycling and the recent low-power Wake-Up Radio technology, which have not been addressed in previous energy management and Green IoT surveys.

Hence, the mobile energy transfer method named Adaptive Resonant Beam Charging (ARBC), which comprises of two specially separated components: a transmitter and a receiver (e.g., car, TV), and in some cases, a relay (e.g., UAV) used to relay the energy between the transmitter and receiver.

Characteristics of Mobile Energy Transfer

The various Key Characteristics of mobile energy transfer has been discussed as under:

(i) Flexibility:

MET enables energy to be provided to devices that are difficult to reach or located in remote regions.

(ii) Scalability:

The mobility feature enables the energy distribution mechanism to scale to meet an increasing number of IoT devices.

(iii) Efficiency:

By directly targeting devices that require power, MET can increase the overall energy efficiency of the network.

the mobile base station, the number of devices, their tolerable time for delivering data and energy, and the transmission powers required for energy and data transfer.

The hierarchical and wireless energy transfer mechanism for wireless rechargeable sensor networks that employs mobile chargers.

(iii) Disaster Recovery: Can supply emergency power to IoT devices used in disaster management and recovery activities.

Challenges of MET: Efficiently navigating and coordinating mobile energy carriers to supply energy to appropriate devices.

Energy Efficiency: The wireless energy transfer mechanism must be efficient in order to avoid transmission losses. Security involves protecting the energy transfer process from potential security threats and guaranteeing consistent energy supply.

Green Computing

Green computing Green computing is the study and practice of ecologically sustainable computing. This technique tries to reduce overall power consumption using measures such as improving network infrastructure by reducing the number of servers, switches, and cables, as well as applying new power utilization algorithms.

Sleep/Wake-Up Techniques

Wake-Up Radio represents a novel hardware

Applications of MET:**(i)Remote Monitoring:**

The deal for IoT devices installed in remote or difficult-to-reach locations where standard power sources are inconvenient.

(ii)Agricultural IoT: Useful in agricultural applications where IoT sensors are dispersed across broad fields and require frequent recharge.

described in featuring a microcontroller unit connected to a main radio and a wake-up receiver[10].

During most of its operation, the microcontroller and main radio remain in deep sleep mode and when the wake-up receiver detects a wake-up signal transmitted by an external node, it triggers an interrupt signal to awaken the microcontroller. The microcontroller then performs specified tasks and transmits data via its main radio.

According to building a wake-up radio for usage in bigger contexts requires considering many essential design aspects:

Power Consumption: The node's power consumption must not surpass the main radio's sleep power in order to maintain a balance between energy saved during sleep and energy required when active.

Time to Wake-Up: Reducing the time necessary to wake up the device's radio is critical for

solution designed to significantly reduce the energy consumption of devices and extend network lifetimes. This technology involves integrating a low-power radio alongside the device's main radio, which activates the device from deep sleep upon sensing an incoming signal. In IoT systems, a Wake-Up Radio

supporting environmentally sustainable cloud computing activities.

the transmitter end.

Communication Range: The range of a wake-up radio influences its application type and overall power consumption. For example, shorter communication ranges may necessitate multi-hop communication, which increases node density and power consumption.

Data Rate: Higher data rates in Wake-Up Radios can improve energy efficiency and minimize wake-up time. Furthermore, higher bit lengths can increase the communication range and dependability of wake-up signals.

Cost and size: Wake-Up Radios must be cost-effective in order to integrate with IoT settings and existing sensor nodes.

Cloud Data Centres and Energy Consumption:

The number of cloud-based data centers is continuously increasing as computing

lowering latency and broadening the variety of applications for which wake-up radios may be effectively used.

False Wake-Ups and Interference: Issues like as interference and improper receipt of signals meant for other devices can cause nodes to be activated unnecessarily, wasting significant energy. Designers must identify acceptable methods to reduce these difficulties without increasing total energy.

Sensitivity:

The sensitivity of the receiving node in a wake-up radio environment has a substantial impact on power demand. High sensitivity demands more power at the receiver end, whereas poor sensitivity necessitates greater radiated power at centered on third-party considerations, which includes two types of inventories: green offers and carbon emissions.

These repositories allow users and providers to offer and use green services. Green agents access services from the green offer repository and arrange them to minimize CO₂ emissions,

5. GreenCloud Computing (GCC)

The GreenCloud Computing (GCC) Green Cloud Computing (GCC) techniques attempt to save energy while simultaneously lowering operational expenses and improving environmental sustainability.

Cloud computing provides utility-based services

resources become more in demand. As a result, the energy consumption of these data centers is also increasing. Power-aware scheduling, variable resource management, live migration, and minimum virtual machine design are used to increase overall system efficiency in data center-based clouds while incurring low performance overhead[11].

to optimize computer resources while reducing energy use.

Advantages of Green cloud computing:

Green cloud computing offers advantages such as reduced time and cost, as well as intuitive upgrades.

The GCC contributes to a green cloud structure

- Reliability and fault tolerance , Ease of use ,
- Improved storage , Flexibility , Reduced energy use , Reduced calculating time , No requirement for software or hardware updates , Accessible from any program or location , Unlimited use , Constant availability , Excellent service quality.

Green IoT networks

The green IOT networks aim to create ecologically friendly and energy-efficient infrastructures within the Internet of Things (IoT) domain.

These networks seek to reduce the environmental implications of standard IoT setups by reducing energy usage, supporting eco-friendly hardware, and lowering overall

around the world, but the data centers that serve these applications use a lot of energy, which contributes to high operational costs and large carbon dioxide emissions[12].

This excessive energy use also raises the level of hazardous gasses in the environment. A cloud is a distributed computing system that includes networked and virtualized machines. Green Cloud computer, often known as Green IT, aims device battery life and lowering energy consumption while in use. The use of renewable or recyclable energy sources is an important aspect of green IoT networks.

By incorporating solar, wind, water, or other renewable energy options, these networks reduce dependence on traditional energy sources[14].

Improving energy efficiency through green cloud computing

Green cloud computing improves energy efficiency by developing, creating, and utilizing recyclable resources and services in an environmentally responsible manner. The major goal is to reduce the environmental impact of data centres and cloud infrastructure, which are renowned for consuming large amounts of energy and releasing carbon.

The key methods and technologies used in green cloud computing are:

Energy-efficient data centers use improved cooling systems, optimized server gear (such as

carbon footprints[13].

Various key efforts include optimizing the energy consumption of IoT devices by developing energy-efficient hardware and implementing energy-saving algorithms, which frequently employ machine learning techniques. Green IoT networks help to create a more sustainable ecosystem by increasing

during periods of low utilization by modifying resource allocation to meet workload needs.

Green or recyclable data center locations:

Locating data centers in areas with access to renewable energy sources (such as solar or wind power) and cooler weather can dramatically cut energy usage for cooling systems. Locating data centers in such environments reduces operational costs and environmental impact.

Energy-efficient hardware: Integrating energy-efficient components such as processors, storage devices, and networking equipment improves energy efficiency in data centers. These components are designed to execute jobs with minimal power consumption while maintaining performance.

Green cloud computing attempts to improve energy efficiency across data centers and cloud services through the implementation of these solutions. This technique not only lowers operational expenses, but it also helps to

low-power processors), and incorporate renewable energy sources into their operations. These techniques are designed to reduce overall energy consumption and carbon emissions[15].

Dynamic resource allocation: Cloud platforms scale resources up and down in real time to meet demand. This strategy reduces energy waste

sustainability: Low-power components and energy-efficient microcontrollers:

Low power components:Using power-saving components is crucial for increasing the battery life of IoT devices.

Energy-efficient microcontroller chips enable to optimize energy consumption without sacrificing device performance.

Recyclable hardware: Using recyclable materials in IoT device manufacture helps to reduce electronic waste and promotes a circular economy approach.

Energy harvesting:Energy harvesting research enables Internet of Things devices to absorb and use ambient energy sources such as solar, kinetic, or thermal energy. This strategy reduces reliance on traditional power sources while increasing the sustainability of IoT activities.

Integration of renewable energy sources: As with Green Cloud initiatives, including renewable energy sources such as solar power into IoT deployments decreases the environmental impact of energy usage. Solar-

promote environmental sustainability by reducing the carbon footprint of cloud computing equipment.

Improving the Energy Efficiency through Green IoT

Improving energy efficiency with Green IoT entails many main methods targeted at lowering power usage and increasing renewable energy utilization reduces overall energy consumption and carbon emissions.

Designing energy-efficient devices: Creating IoT devices with energy-efficient designs, such as sleep/wake-up modes, efficient data transmission protocols, and low power consumption during idle states, can dramatically improve energy efficiency.

Future of green cloud computing:

The future advancements in Green IoT and Green Cloud Computing promise to revolutionize how we approach sustainability and efficiency in digital technologies. Green IoT, focusing on environmentally friendly and energy-efficient IoT infrastructure, will continue to evolve with innovations in several critical areas[16].

These include the development of ultra-low-power chipsets and energy-harvesting technologies, which will extend the battery life of devices and reduce reliance on traditional

powered sensors and gadgets provide sustainable solutions, especially in rural or off-grid areas where access to standard power networks is limited.

Optimizing data center operations: In IoT-enabled cloud computing environments, optimizing data center operations through virtualization, improved cooling systems, and

Similarly, Green Cloud Computing (GCC) will advance by enhancing data center efficiency through advanced cooling systems, optimized server hardware, and increased integration of renewable energy sources like solar and wind power.

Smart energy management systems will dynamically allocate resources based on demand, minimizing energy waste during low usage periods. The scalability and flexibility of GCC platforms will also improve, allowing businesses to efficiently scale their computing resources while maintaining high energy efficiency standards[17].

. Smart energy management systems will allocate resources dynamically based on demand, reducing energy waste during low-use hours. The scalability and flexibility of GCC platforms will improve, letting organizations to efficiently scale their computing capabilities while maintaining high energy efficiency standards.

Both Green IoT and GCC will prioritize sustainability by employing green design

power sources. Integration with mobile cloud computing through sensorcloud architectures will optimize data transmission and processing, particularly in smart city applications aimed at enhancing environmental sustainability.

systems will prioritize user health and safety while minimizing environmental impact[18].

Conclusion:

Improving energy efficiency in IoT networks by combining green cloud computing and machine learning is a significant step toward sustainability and operational efficiency. The Green cloud computing is critical in improving data center operations, leveraging renewable energy sources, and implementing dynamic resource allocation algorithms.

These techniques not only minimize the carbon footprint of cloud services, but also help to save electricity in IoT deployments. Green cloud computing improves efficiency while maintaining performance and scalability by carefully selecting data center sites and using energy-efficient hardware.

Machine learning improves energy efficiency in IoT networks by allowing for intelligent decision-making and predictive analytics. Algorithms can optimize device operations,

principles such as eco-friendly materials and reducing environmental effect. This involves minimizing electronic waste and maximizing resource utilization throughout the lifecycle of IoT devices and cloud infrastructures. Furthermore, the design and deployment of these

plan jobs to save energy during peak hours, and forecast maintenance requirements to avoid energy-wasting failures.

This functionality not only extends the life of IoT devices, but also improves their operational efficiency, thereby contributing to sustainable practices.

To summarize, the combination of green cloud computing and machine learning presents a promising avenue to improving energy efficiency in IoT networks. Organizations that integrate these technologies can achieve considerable savings in energy usage, cut operational costs, and maintain environmental sustainability goals in an increasingly connected and data-driven world. As these technologies mature, they have the ability to effect dramatic shifts towards greener and more efficient IoT ecosystem.

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